

Ensemble Graph Attention Networks for Cellular Network Analytics: From Model Creation to Explainability

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Abstract—In automated radio network control, understanding the effect of different factors on network performance is crucial. Although there are machine learning (ML) solutions that can reliably anticipate network performance expressed as key performance indicator (KPI) values, these models are typically black-box or provide only partial explanations. Most approaches are based on flat data structures and cannot exploit the graph nature of the data, being unable to quantify neighbors' impact. In this paper, we propose a new graph neural network-based model called Ensemble Graph Attention Network (Ensemble GAT) for network KPI prediction. We show that the proposed model results in better or comparable KPI prediction performance to the state-of-the-art while also carrying information about links between neighboring cells. In addition to model creation, we investigate how explainable AI solutions can be used to provide root-cause explanations for network KPI degradation. To generate feature attributions, we introduce an adapted version of GraphLime that works with ensemble models. In addition, we propose a new technique called Neighbor Perturbation to identify the neighboring cells that have the most significant impact on KPI prediction. We demonstrate the effectiveness of these models on both synthetic and real-world datasets.

Index Terms—Network Management, Graph Attention Network, Explainable AI, KPI Prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

Advanced network observability and analytics are essential for high-quality network management in mobile cellular networks. Obtaining meaningful insights into the network operation is essential for performing (either manually or automatically) the proper actions when necessary, thus optimizing network performance. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) [1] have been introduced as the main descriptors of network performance. Different KPI definitions exist, catching various aspects of the expected operation.

A low KPI value indicates some problem in the network that needs to be investigated to get a proper diagnosis. Root-cause analysis (RCA) is the process of identifying the primary source of performance degradation. After finding the root cause, the operator can potentially take further actions to fix the problem or improve the network to avoid similar issues in the future.

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RCA is often part of a closed loop, and mitigation actions are taken automatically.

Performance in Radio Access Networks (RAN) is typically measured via cell-level KPIs. Cell KPIs depend on various factors, such as traffic characteristics, load, cell configuration, radio conditions, and even the physical environment. Due to the complexity of the problem space, data-driven methods are often used for analytics and RCA. Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML) methods are applied to train models based on system logs and datasets from earlier operational scenarios to predict the KPI. In most 5G deployments, data collection is implemented by a central Network Management System (NMS) responsible for monitoring and configuring network elements and storing all the related information and time series in a database. NMS allows training AI/ML models on previously collected data. Predicting the KPI in itself is a good tool for the timely identification of performance issues. However, it cannot reveal the root cause of the problem and thus cannot provide hints on how to handle it.

As mobile networks become increasingly complex, the need for automated operation is emerging. The key promise of Beyond-5G and 6G architecture proposals [2], [3] is the automated operation through AI-driven network control and management. The proposed systems are flexibly and efficiently optimized through learning and adaptation to satisfy extreme performance KPIs and SLAs. In addition to good predictive models, this kind of automated operation also requires explainability techniques to identify the root cause of KPI degradations and SLA violations and select effective mitigation actions.

Different techniques have emerged to explain trained ML models, highlighting the most relevant features contributing to the KPI value. However, most model explainers have been designed for methods working with tabular data. In cellular networks, each row represents a cell with its own features and some aggregated features (mean, max, min, percentiles, etc.) derived from the neighboring cells. It has been shown in [4] that advanced tabular models like XGBoost and LightGBM result in good performance, and efficient methodologies (SHAP, LIME) exist to explain and interpret these models in an RCA process.

It is easy to see that the flat tabular representation cannot capture the graph structure of cellular networks, and the aggregation hides the details needed for a detailed RCA

process. For example, different neighboring cells may have different impacts on the KPI degradation, which is fully hidden by the aggregated features. In cell-level monitoring, when the neighboring cells are also considered (apart from the local features of the given cell), a graph-structured dataset gives a more fine-grained representation. Different ML models operating on graph data have emerged in the past years. Graph Neural Network (GNN) [5] is the most used ML technique for graphs. Using these models, we can predict cell KPIs based on the local and neighboring features using the graph structure of the data. This way, the KPI of a given cell depends on the features of the local cell and the nearby cells' features; neighboring information is available via the links in the graph. Though GNN-based models have good predicting capabilities, building explainers for such models is more challenging than the previously discussed tree-based models. Neighboring cells may have a significant impact on a given cell. For example, interference effects might degrade the performance if the cell areas overlap. Another example is that two neighboring cells share the same spectrum. In both cases, the load of one cell highly impacts the performance of the other cell.

Fig. 1: Explainable model structure

The traditional process of ML-based RCA [4], [6] is the following: 1) train a supervised ML model for KPI prediction with good prediction performance; 2) build an explainer based on the trained model; 3) make prediction (inference) on the KPI value; 4) derive the feature impact factors by the explainer; 5) highlight the most impactful features as potential contributors for the particular network problem. A high-level architecture of this approach is presented in Figure 1. One can observe that this process can only highlight a set of features impacting the KPI prediction, while the impact of neighbors remains undiscovered.

In this paper, we focus on building an explainable model for predicting cell KPIs in cellular networks. In such an environment, the neighbor impact is as important as the feature impact. The proposed model is based on GNN combined with the principle of ensemble learning to obtain a more accurate model. Then in addition to feature importance, we also propose a new model-explaining method to get insight into the neighbor impact in the final prediction. In addition to comparing traditional ML models, we also evaluate the proposed method against a recently published explainable model [4].

The main contributions of this work are the following:

- We build a GNN-based model to predict cell performance utilizing the cell's own features, neighbor cells' features and cell relations' features.
- We improve the prediction performance by combining GNN with ensemble learning to optimally handle multiple

graph snapshots evolving in time (i.e., graphs captured at different instances of time).

- We modify an existing GNN explainer called GraphLime [7] and propose a new method called Neighbor Perturbation that can work with the trained ensemble model and highlight the most impacting features and the most impacting neighbor cells.
- We evaluate our method on both synthetic and real cellular network data, show that it fits the proposed telecom use case well, and compare the results to recent methods. While our GNN-based approach provides better or comparable performance to state-of-the-art solutions, it also has the practical advantage of identifying the most impacting neighbor cell in addition to the most important features.

II. RELATED WORK

There is an increased demand for explainable machine learning (XML) solutions in telecom use cases as more complex machine learning (ML) applications are used to automate network operations [8], [9].

There are several examples where XML was applied successfully in telecom use cases. One example is root cause identification of service-level assurance (SLA) violations. In 5G networks the quality-of-service must be guaranteed according to the service-level agreement the slices have agreed to fulfil. The authors in [10] apply several explainability methods to analyse this problem and identify the important features contributing to the decision. Another emerging track is the application of Explainable AI (XAI) in network security. An exhaustive assessment of the most cutting-edge AI, XAI, beyond 5G technologies, and security aspects are presented in [11].

In [12] radio resource management tasks are formulated as graph optimization problems. Graph neural networks are used successfully for these network management solutions. For model interpretability the equivalence between the graph neural networks and a family of distributed optimization algorithms is showed.

Another graph neural network interpretation technique is presented in [13], where the objective is to find discrete masks for explaining the model, while minimizing the expected deviation from the underlying model's prediction. Although the explanations presented in the article are sparse, the greedy mask selection algorithm they show may lead to local optimal explanations.

A method called GNNExplainer is described in [14]. This model-agnostic approach was designed for providing interpretable explanations for predictions of any GNN-based model. Even though different regularization terms are employed to encourage optimized masks to be discrete, the obtained masks are still soft masks so that GNNExplainer cannot avoid the "introduced evidence" problem, meaning that the provided explanations may present such combination of the features that cannot occur in real life.

The use case that we are targeting at is root cause analysis of KPI degradation. The goal is to predict future KPI degradations and also find the potential cause of the degradation.

In previous works, tree-based algorithms and the SHAP explainability method have been identified as the best suitable methods for this problem [4], [6].

In the following, we are presenting the related work from two aspects. The first one is a brief review of GNN development and recent advances in the field, the second one is a quick summary of explanation methods for graph neural networks.

A. Graph Neural Networks

Graph neural networks [5] first extended neural network architectures to graphs. Based on the model architecture and training strategy the existing methods can be divided into five categories: graph recurrent neural networks (Graph RNNs), graph convolutional networks (GCNs), graph autoencoders (GAEs), graph reinforcement learning (Graph RL), and graph adversarial methods. [15]

GCNs are considered one of the basic GNN variants, they are the hottest topic in graph-based deep learning. Graph convolutions can be divided into two groups: spectral convolutions, which are defined in the spectral domain based on graph Fourier transform or its extensions, and spatial convolutions, which perform convolution by considering node neighborhoods. Bruna et al. [16] first introduced convolution for graph data from the spectral domain using the graph Laplacian matrix [17]. One drawback of this method is that the filters this model computed are non-spatially localized. In spectral GCNs, in general, the node neighborhoods are aggregated with equal or pre-defined weights. However, the impacts of neighbors can vary greatly; thus, they should be learned during training rather than being predetermined. To dynamically aggregate node features Velickovic et al. [18] proposed graph attention networks (GATs) by integrating the attention mechanism [19] into the convolutional layer. EGAT [20] relies on a similar attention mechanism as GAT, but the architecture of the model is different. The edge information is updated as well, not only the node information. A multi-scale merge strategy is followed, meaning that the outputs of all the network layers are concatenated in a final layer to form the final predictions.

B. Interpretation Methods for Graph Neural Networks

Despite the strength of GNN models, they do not allow for human-readable explanations of their predictions. In order to maintain transparency and trust in the decision making process, an interpretable solution is required. The field of explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) deals with the generation of high-quality, intuitive explanations of model decisions [21]. An explanation is a way to verify the output of the model. For example, in the cellular network domain an explanation may consist of a set of important features that effect the performance of the network the most or it may highlight the critical relations between the cells that influence the model decisions. Heavy research have been conducted recently to improve XAI solutions. Yuan et al. [22] categorize the literature into four main tracks:

- The gradients / features-based methods directly employ the squared values of gradients as the importance scores

of different input features. It can be directly computed by back-propagation, which is the same as network training but the targets are input features instead of model parameters. (e.g., Sensitivity Analysis [23], Guided Backpropagation [23], CAM/Grad-CAM [24])

- The perturbation-based methods monitor the change of prediction with respect to different input perturbations to study input importance scores. (e.g., GNNExplainer [14], PGExplainer [25], GraphMask [26], ZORRO [13], Causal Screening [27])
- Surrogate methods first sample the dataset from the neighbors of the given example. Next, these methods fit a simple and interpretable model to the sampled dataset. Then the explanations from the surrogate model are used to explain the original predictions.(e.g., GraphLime [7], RelEx [28], PGM-Explainer [29])
- Decomposition Methods decomposes the output prediction score to different node importance scores. (e.g., LRP [23], Excitation Backpropagation [24], GNN-LRP [30])

III. METHOD

In this section, we provide a brief system overview and present the proposed Ensemble Graph Attention Network and explainability techniques for root-cause analysis in cellular networks.

A. System overview

In mobile telecommunication networks, the network elements (e.g., Radio Base Stations (RBS), Core Network nodes, Transport Network nodes) are managed by the central Network Management System (NMS). The method proposed in this paper could be used to manage RBSs (i.e., cells). NMS also includes Configuration Management (CM) needed for the configuration of network elements as depicted in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: RBSs are managed by central NMS

All CM data related to RBSs and cells (including cell local configuration and cell relations) are stored in the NMS. NMS also provides Performance Monitoring (PM), where various parameters related to user-activities, amount of traffic, load, interference, etc., are measured regularly at the network elements and the result is sent to NMS. PM data can be either periodically reported values of some measures via, e.g., counters, gauges, histograms, or event reports. The CM and PM data can be further processed in NMS by running data analytics to provide proper insights to the operating network engineers or use it in automation scenarios.

B. Main components

The large amount of CM and PM data enables for using AI technologies. In this paper we use explainable AI to get the feature impact factors of certain predictions of the ML model. Here we focus on GNN models where the nodes of the graph are the mobile cells, and the edges are cell relations. The cell pairs having a cell relation are neighbor cells. Handovers of mobile terminals are possible between neighbor cells.

Neighbor cells may impact each other in different ways. If the neighbor cells use overlapping frequency ranges, radio interference might occur either in the uplink or downlink direction, typically at the cell edge. If the neighbor cells are configured to use the same spectrum simultaneously and shared dynamically, they will naturally impact each other via the spectrum resource. If load balancing is configured between the neighbor cells, they will impact each other via the load balancing procedure.

The basic components of our approach (shown in Figure 3) are the GNN model and the GNN explainer. In the first phase, the GNN model is trained to predict a given KPI for each cell. The ground truth data is provided by measuring the KPI values. In parallel, a GNN explainer is built up that maintains the dependencies of the KPI on the features and the neighbor cells. Then, the explainer can determine the most influencing features and the most influencing neighbors.

Fig. 3: Training of the explainable model: at first a GNN model is trained for node-level prediction and then a GNN explainer is built up to interpret the prediction results.

In the second phase, we first use the GNN model for KPI inference, and then the GNN explainer is applied to highlight the main impacting factors influencing the KPI as illustrated in Figure 4. The impacting factors are a set of features influencing the KPI and a set of neighbor cells having a high impact on the inspected cell. The inference is performed regularly for each cell. In a typical setup, the KPI and the feature values are collected in certain periods (e.g., in every 15 mins), and time instances of the inference can be adapted to these periods.

Fig. 4: Inference from the model and the explainer: the GNN model is applied for KPI inference and then feature and neighbor importance is derived by the GNN explainer.

During operation, the model accuracy should be checked periodically. If the accuracy is good enough, then the impacting features reflect the cause of the problem; otherwise, the model should be re-trained with new data.

C. Ensemble GNN model

The input of the conventional GNN model is one graph with node features and, optionally, edge features. Then, an abstract representation (also called embedding) is created for each node in the graph, considering the features of the surrounding nodes and edges. Nearest neighbors or, in general, neighbors within a hop limit can also be considered. The number of neighboring hops included in the calculation is determined by the number of layers in the GNN. Lastly, node predictions are generated from the embeddings. Several types of GNNs are known according to how the calculation method is implemented.

We considered multiple aspects when selecting the appropriate GNN candidates for our problem. We studied only those convolution types that are capable of utilizing not only the node but also the edge information. We also paid attention to the generalization capability and the computational demands of the models. However, most importantly, we were looking for convolutions in which the unique effect of the neighbors could prevail as much as possible. That criteria led our focus from spectral convolutions (GCNs), where a fixed or learnable polynomial of Laplacian or adjacency matrix is used to aggregate node information, to spatial convolutions, especially to graph attention networks (GAT). Unlike GCNs, where the weights in neighbor node feature aggregation are independent of the feature values and depend solely on the graph topological structure, the weights in GAT are a function of node content due to the attentional mechanism.

1) *GAT*: In the original GAT model [18], the attention mechanism was only defined on the node features of the neighborhood and did not take edge features into account. The architecture of GAT follows the general multi-layered approach of GNNs; it is composed of several (usually not as many as a traditional CNN, these networks are typically shallow) stacked graph attention layers. The input of the original graph attention layer is a set of node features, $h = \{\vec{h}_1, \vec{h}_2, \dots, \vec{h}_N\}$, $\vec{h}_i \in \mathbb{R}^F$, where N is the number of nodes, and F is the number of features in each node. The output of the layer is a set of new node features (embeddings) with potentially different sizes $h' = \{\vec{h}'_1, \vec{h}'_2, \dots, \vec{h}'_N\}$, $\vec{h}'_i \in \mathbb{R}^{F'}$. The computation of the new node embeddings is the following: at first, a shared linear transformation, $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{F' \times F}$, is applied on every node, then with a shared attentional mechanism, $a : \mathbb{R}^{F'} \times \mathbb{R}^{F'} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, the attention coefficient e_{ij} (the weight that indicates the importance of neighbor j when computing the new embedding of node i) is computed for all $j \in \mathcal{N}_i$, where \mathcal{N}_i is some neighborhood of node i in the graph (in case of self-loops, \mathcal{N}_i may contain node i itself):

$$e_{ij} = a(\mathbf{W}\vec{h}_i, \mathbf{W}\vec{h}_j).$$

A softmax function is applied on the attention coefficients to make them comparable across all nodes:

$$\alpha_{ij} = \text{softmax}_j(e_{ij}) = \frac{\exp(e_{ij})}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_i} \exp(e_{ik})}. \quad (1)$$

The final output is the linear combination of the normalized attention coefficients and the features corresponding to them:

$$\vec{h}'_i = \sigma \left(\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \alpha_{ij} \mathbf{W} \vec{h}_j \right), \quad (2)$$

where σ denotes a nonlinear function.

The learning process can be stabilized if Equation 2 is applied not only once, but K times and the different results are concatenated in the middle layers:

$$\vec{h}'_i = \left\| \sigma \left(\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \alpha_{ij}^k \mathbf{W}^k \vec{h}_j \right) \right\|_{k=1}^K,$$

and averaged in the final layer:

$$\vec{h}'_i = \sigma \left(\frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \alpha_{ij}^k \mathbf{W}^k \vec{h}_j \right).$$

The GAT model used in our experiments differs from the original version in two points. Firstly, the original GAT solution was sensitive to the static attention problem, meaning that the ranking of the attention scores was unconditioned on the query node. This problem was addressed by Brody et al. in [31] with a simple fix by modifying the order of operations in Equation 2. Secondly, the version we applied utilizes multidimensional edge features \mathbf{e}_{ij} and modifies the computation of the attention score by concatenating the edge feature to the node features in Equation 3. Regarding the attention mechanism a and the nonlinearity σ , we kept the same functions that were used in the original GAT version: a single-layer feedforward neural network, parameterized by $\vec{\mathbf{a}} \in \mathbb{R}^{2F'}$ was used as the attention mechanism and the LeakyReLU nonlinearity was applied as σ . The final attention coefficients used in our experiments may be expressed as:

$$\alpha_{ij} = \frac{\exp \left(\vec{\mathbf{a}} \text{LeakyReLU} \left(\mathbf{W} \left[\vec{h}_i \parallel \vec{h}_j \parallel \mathbf{e}_{ij} \right] \right) \right)}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_i} \exp \left(\vec{\mathbf{a}} \text{LeakyReLU} \left(\mathbf{W} \left[\vec{h}_i \parallel \vec{h}_k \parallel \mathbf{e}_{ik} \right] \right) \right)} \quad (3)$$

2) *Ensemble GAT*: The dataset obtained in periodic data collection provides multiple snapshots of the same graph structure. These snapshots present different characteristics depending on the time of the day when they were recorded. The network load in the afternoon is typically higher, and the probability of throughput degradation is increased compared to those snapshots that fall outside of the peak hours. This phenomenon greatly influences the performance of the GNN model. There are different ways to apply GNN models to the set of graph snapshots. One option is aggregating the features over the snapshots and applying state-of-the-art GNN architectures on the single aggregated graph. This way, valuable information is lost in the aggregation step. Another option is to train a state-of-the-art GNN model on the union of the snapshots. In the case of many snapshots, this method can become computationally intractable. Moreover, the snapshots are handled equally, which has limitations and thus negatively

impacts the model's performance. Following the known concept of ensemble learning, we propose Ensemble GNN method (an ensemble of several GNNs as base estimators) to handle multiple graph snapshots optimally. Ensembles are known to improve the accuracy, stability and robustness of machine learning systems [32]. The schematic diagram of the proposed Ensemble GNN model is shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: The proposed ensemble GAT model: The base estimators are trained on the bootstrapped subsets of $Dataset_1$. GAT0 model is used to calculate the weights of different snapshots of $Dataset_1$, expressing the model's performance on the snapshots. Finally, an XGBoost model combines the outputs of base estimators and provides a final prediction.

The Ensemble GAT model is built up in the following way:

- Let $\mathcal{G} = [sn_1, \dots, sn_m]$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $m \geq 4$ be the list of all the available graph snapshots in chronological order. \mathcal{G} is split into four disjoint subsets: $Dataset_i = \{sn_j\}$, s.t. $j \equiv i \pmod{4}$, $i \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$. That way it is ensured that each subset contains an equal proportion of elements from and outside the peak period.
- A GAT model (GAT0 on Figure 5) is trained on $Dataset_0$. This model is used to make predictions on $Dataset_1$ and the root mean squared errors of the model $\mathcal{E} = [err_1, \dots, err_k]$ are computed for all the k snapshots in $Dataset_1$.
- Bootstrapping: the snapshots of $Dataset_1$ are sampled with replacement and with unequal selection probabilities n times to derive multiple different subsets of the snapshots (Set_1, \dots, Set_n on figure 5) as inputs for the different base estimator GAT trainings of the ensemble model. The probability of snapshot sn_x ($x \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, $x \leq n$) to be selected is inversely proportional to the min-max normalized value of GAT0's mean squared error on snapshot sn_x and may be expressed as:

$$p_x = 1 - \frac{err_x - \min(\mathcal{E})}{\max(\mathcal{E}) - \min(\mathcal{E})}.$$

- n GAT models are trained separately on the snapshot sets Set_1, \dots, Set_n , so that n base estimator GAT models are generated. All the n models are used to make predictions on the same dataset, $Dataset_2$ and the sets $Output_1, \dots, Output_n$ are formed from the base estimator predictions correspondingly.
- At this point for every node in the graph we have n different predictions and we also have the original label, meaning that a new model can be trained on the base estimator outputs to combine the results and obtain a final prediction. In our experiment we choose an XGBoost [33] model for this final combination.

D. Ensemble GNN explainer

To interpret the predictions of the Ensemble GAT model, we present two techniques: one for feature explanations and another for calculating neighbor impact. The explainability techniques are applied to the base estimators first, and then the results are combined to form the final interpretations of the ensemble.

Various known explainers, including GraphLime [7], can be adapted to generate the impact factors. GraphLime, a well-known choice for generating feature impacts, uses a surrogate model built on a subset of the original dataset to provide feature explanations. The adaptability of this method allows us to use the explanations of the interpretable model to explain the GNN. GraphLime starts by identifying a subgraph around the target node from its N-hop neighborhood that is eligible for the model to make the right predictions. Then, a Hilbert-Schmidt Independence Criterion Lasso (HSIC) is built on the subgraph, a nonlinear and supervised feature selection algorithm. The result is an importance score for every feature, empowering us to understand how the features affected the prediction of the target node.

The calculation of feature importances in the Ensemble GAT model starts by applying GraphLime on all the n base estimator models of the trained ensemble. Let's suppose that there are k node features and the output of GraphLime for the i -th base estimator is $\beta^i = (\beta_1^i, \dots, \beta_k^i)$ for a given target node. To obtain the final feature importance values for the ensemble model, the weighted average of the base estimators' GraphLime results is calculated:

$$\beta_{\text{Ens}} = \sum_{j=1}^n g_j \beta^j,$$

where, g_j ($j \in \mathbb{N}$, $j \leq n$) is the gain corresponding to the j -th base estimator in the XGBoost model. In general, the gain is the main reference factor of the importance of a feature in the tree branches; it shows the average improvement in accuracy brought by a feature's output to the branches it is on [34]. In our context, the gain represents the relative importance of the base estimators in the ensemble model. Weighting the output of GraphLime for the base estimators with XGBoost gain instead of using an unweighted average gives more reliable results. In the following, we refer to this technique as the Ensembled GraphLime method. Although GraphLime is powerful in recognizing feature importance, it cannot provide information about how each neighbor affects the prediction.

Fig. 6: Schematic view of neighbor perturbation: the absolute values of the differences between the original prediction and the prediction when one neighbor is deleted are clustered. The cluster with the highest difference average corresponds to the neighbors that effect the prediction the most.

The neighbor perturbation method, as summarized in Figure 6, is a significant addition to our toolkit. It allows us to gain insights on neighbor impacts by deleting the edges connected to the target node to be explained one after another, and collecting the change in the model prediction for the different input. The differences compared to the prediction with the full neighborhood can be used to quantify neighbor importance. The neighbors of the target node are then clustered based on the differences in prediction. The cluster with the highest average difference is finally selected as it contains the most relevant neighbors.

The neighbor perturbation method is applied to each base model to generate the neighbor impacts for the Ensemble GNN model. Each difference in prediction between the perturbed

graph and the original graph is aggregated for each graph node. The aggregation is performed similarly as in the case of feature impact calculation: XGBoost gain is used to form the weighted average of the base model differences, and then X-means [35] clustering is applied. X-means is an improved version of the well-known K-means [36] clustering algorithm; its biggest advantage is that the number of clusters does not have to be supplied in advance.

IV. DATA SETS

Measuring explainability without ground-truth knowledge is a challenging task. To perform the validation we tested our solution on several datasets of different nature.

A. Synthetic dataset

The purpose of the synthetic dataset was to provide ground-truth for validating the explainability methods. We aimed to simulate a simple scenario when there is one neighbor that affects the target node's KPI. Let us assume that we are examining the situation when the increased load of one cell reduces the performance of the local cell. How would this appear at the level of feature values? We would see that the KPI value of the local cell is low, and there is at least one neighbor whose load value is extremely high. With the star graph topology, we wanted to simulate this situation in the synthetic data and see if our method can predict the local node's KPI and if the explanation model can find the right neighbor and the right feature, on which we made the local KPI value dependent.

Star graph topology: A union of 10000 star graphs of order six. Initially, each node has eight random features chosen from an uniform distribution in the interval $(0, 0.6)$. In half of the stars, one feature f of one neighbor is set to 1. Each center node has a binary KPI, dependent only on the value of feature f of one particular neighbor. If the given feature was higher than a threshold, the KPI was 1 and 0 otherwise.

B. Real dataset

Fig. 7: Graph structured dataset to represent cell features and relations. f_1, f_2, \dots and e_1, e_2, \dots represent the node and the edge features correspondingly. Every node has a KPI value as well, that is going to be the target of the prediction task in our use case.

This dataset contains 23 hours of LTE network data. As illustrated in Figure 7, the network is represented as a graph. There are 244694 vertices in the graph that represent the network cells and 976958 edges that represent the cell neighborhood. Each cell has several features (f) and a KPI value, that is, the average downlink throughput of the cell. Initially, there were 285 node features containing configuration data and performance measurement data collected from the network nodes according to the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) standard specifications [37], [38]. We selected the 52 most relevant features for model training based on setting a maximum threshold for feature correlations and a minimum threshold for the mutual information of the features with the KPI. One-hot encoding was applied to the categorical features. Apart from the cell features, the graph edges (i.e., cell relations) also have three features (e).

Importantly, the features are collected at regular intervals (e.g., every 15 minutes). Some features (e.g., user traffic, network load) change frequently, while others (e.g., configuration settings) remain constant for extended periods. It can also be assumed that the graph structure does not change frequently. This approach results in multiple graphs with the same structure captured at different time points (i.e., snapshots). Figure 8 below illustrates this concept, providing a visual representation of multiple snapshots.

Fig. 8: Multiple snapshots of the same graph structure. The topology of the graph remains untouched, only the node and the edge features change.

In order to reduce complexity, features are organized into categories. The list of the main metrics used in the analysis including KPIs and feature categories is shown in Table I:

C. Real dataset with artificial KPI

This dataset relies on the previously described real dataset, but the original KPI was substituted with a synthetic KPI we defined for validation purposes. Due to the unavailability or limited availability of ground-truth data for real KPIs, we designed an artificial KPI to serve as a proxy ground truth. This synthetic KPI was designed similarly to the KPI used in the star graph topology, where a central node is connected to several neighbors. The synthetic KPI was defined based on a simple rule: if a selected feature of one particular neighbor exceeded a predefined threshold, the KPI was set to 1; otherwise, it was set to 0. This approach allowed us to create a controlled environment where the influence of specific features and neighbors on the KPI could be clearly observed and analyzed. The main goal was to develop a dataset where the features were grounded in reality, and the artificial KPI provided a reliable ground truth for both

downlink throughput	Average throughput (i.e. bitrate, measured in Mbits/sec) of data transmissions in the cell experienced by the users
CM_capacity	Maximum data throughput provided by the cell
CM_dimensioning	It represents the characteristics of the physical area of the cell, e.g. height, range, tilt, maximum power
CM_frequency	Radio frequency used in the cell
CM_mimo_and_modulation	Modulation type enabled (e.g. 64QAM or 256QAM) and the number of transmit/receive antennas used in the Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) system of the base station
load	It represents the load of the cell, it can be measured by various metrics such as radio utilization, number of active users in the cell, actual amount of traffic in the cell
neighbor_load	Load of the neighbor cells
interference	It refers to the disturbance of the radio signal by another signal, causing decoding errors and poor data transmission
channel_quality	It represents the conditions of the radio channel, affected by attenuation, noise or interference
path_loss	Attenuation of the signal propagating from the transmitter to the receiver
sub_cell_location	Distance of the User Equipment (UE) from the base station, it can be estimated by measuring the Timing Advance value, that is the round trip propagation delay between the UE and the base station antenna, originally used for synchronisation purposes
UE_capability	It refers to the standard UE category, indicating the number of downlink MIMO layers supported, the maximum datarate uplink and downlink

TABLE I: Categories of metrics collected in the dataset obtained from real measurements (CM stands for Configuration Management data).

model training, performance evaluation, and the validation of the investigated explainability techniques. This methodology highlights the importance of having a reliable ground truth for both performance evaluation and explainability in machine learning models, especially in scenarios where real ground-truth data is scarce or unavailable.

V. RESULTS

We compared the Ensemble GAT model to several state of the art solutions:

- The original GAT model [18] that was detailed in Section III-C1.
- GraphNet [39] is a general graph neural network framework with a block structure. A full GN block consists of three sub-blocks (edge block, node block, global block) that are applied iteratively. A GN block contains three “update” functions and three “aggregation” functions. Based on the GN block configurations, different GraphNet models can be constructed. In our experiments we used the graph network variant referred to as non-local

neural network in the article, which contains only the edge block and the node block.

- XGBoost [33] is an iterative decision tree algorithm with multiple decision trees. Every tree is learning from the residuals of all previous trees. The predicted output of XGBoost is the sum of all the results. XGBoost is efficient, flexible, and has good generalization performance, but since it is a flat model, neighbor information can be incorporated only in the form of aggregates.
- Baseline: the work of Kelen et al. [4] proposes an Explainable AI method to explain the effect of different features on network performance. Their modeling relies on a gradient boosted decision tree, LightGBM [40]. They also address the problem of dependencies among features and feature coalitions and present a new solutions for calculating causality-respecting and additive local feature attributions, by using a conditional Asymmetric SHAP model [41].

Although their solution is effective and reliable, their modeling is not graph-based but relies on tabular approaches, which narrows the explanations to local and aggregated neighbor metrics and excludes the possibility of examining the effect of neighbors separately.

A. Performance of the Prediction Models

After reviewing the literature, we found that considerable prior research posits that many convolutional graph neural networks work by assuming and exploiting homophily assumptions in the underlying graph, meaning that connected nodes have similar labels [42], [43], [44], [45]. However, the network data used in our experiments is heterophilous. This property of the dataset limited our possibilities and we found that out of the two basic types of GNNs, spatial and spectral [46], only the spatial type fits to our problem. Some models had to be excluded immediately due to their cubic complexity [16], [47], others could not perform node-level, only graph-level predictions [48], [49], [50]. Finally we found that GraphNet [39] and GAT [18] are the two GNNs that best fit our problem.

To find the most suitable prediction model, we tried several different methods. The performance of XGBoost, GraphNet, GAT and Ensemble GAT was compared on the same real dataset with a balanced binary KPI. The Ensemble GAT model was composed of six base estimators, each having two GAT convolutional layers and eight attention heads. Table II summarizes the results. The GNN based solutions outperformed the tabular XGBoost model. GAT and GraphNet gave similar results and the Ensemble GAT gave the highest accuracy.

Model	XGBoost	GraphNet	GAT	Ensemble GAT
Acc	79%	81%	81%	84%

TABLE II: Model performance comparison on real data with binary KPI.

Apart from Ensemble GAT, we experimented with two other GAT training architectures to utilize multiple graph snapshots during model training. The first approach involves training

the GAT model snapshot by snapshot: we start by training on one snapshot and after a predefined number of iterations, we change the training data to another snapshot iteratively. Another solution is to unite all the training snapshots into one big graph and train the model on the union. In Table III, the performance of the three training versions and the Baseline is evaluated on the real dataset with a continuous KPI. One can see that the Ensemble GAT model outperforms the other two GAT versions and gives similar results as the Baseline.

Model	GAT sn. by sn.	GAT union of all sn.	Ensemble GAT	Baseline
MSE	0.054	0.036	0.026	0.023

TABLE III: The performance of three different GAT architectures compared to the Baseline on real data with a continuous KPI.

B. Time Complexity Comparison

The resource usage of the GAT algorithm was examined on a graph with 29K nodes with 8 features and 985K edges with 3 edge features. One NVIDIA GPU (GV100GL [Tesla V100 SXM2 16GB]) was used during this experiment. In general, one Ensembled GAT training includes $m + 1$ GAT trainings, if m base estimators are used. The time complexity of one GAT training is a square function of the number of examples. In more details: computing F' features may be expressed as $O(K(|V|FF' + |E|F'))$, where F is the number of input features, K is the number of attention heads and $|V|$ and $|E|$ are the numbers of nodes and edges in the graph, respectively. In practice, the time needed for training in this setup took 33 minutes. The time complexity of XGBoost training is less resourceful, it is logarithmic in the number of examples. More precisely one training takes $O(tdx \log n)$ steps, where t is the number of trees, d is the height of the trees, x is the number of non missing entries and n is the number of examples. In our experimental setup XGBoost needed 12 minutes on average to reach convergence.

Despite the fact that XGBoost is faster, GAT's training time was also affordable in practice. Since GAT makes use of the topological information of the network, we came to the conclusion that this important advantage against XGBoost makes the GAT approach more suitable for our particular use case.

C. Explainability Results on Synthetic or Modified Data

Several modifications have been conducted on the real dataset, and a synthetic dataset have been constructed in order to facilitate the validation of the models for neighbor and feature impact analysis.

1) *Neighbor Impact Validation*: A GAT model was trained on the synthetic dataset, and then neighbor perturbation was applied to the trained model. The GAT model performed with 100% accuracy on this dataset, and neighbor perturbation found the right neighbor in 100% of the cases when the KPI was 1 (when a neighbor contributed to the KPI). In all of the

cases, the candidate cluster contained one element. For the stars where the KPI was 0, and each neighbor contributed to the KPI equally, the correct neighbor was chosen by neighbor perturbation in 20% of the cases. This result is consistent with the performance of random selection.

We repeated the same experiment on the real dataset with artificial KPI. The GAT model's accuracy on this dataset was 94%. Neighbor perturbation was conducted on 12000 nodes. When the KPI was 1, the neighbor cluster contained the right neighbor in 80% of the cases. In 66% of the cases the candidate cluster had only one element. In 90% of the cases the cardinality of the chosen cluster was less than 4.

2) *Feature Impact Validation*: To validate that GraphLime is able to find the right feature, we modified the real dataset: the topology remained the same, but only the eight load features were selected and a new independent random feature was constructed for every node. A new KPI was defined as a linear function of the new feature, hence the new KPI was independent from the original features and depended solely on the new feature. After training an Ensemble GAT model on this dataset, we applied GraphLime as described in Section III-D. Figure 9 shows that GraphLime finds the right feature for almost every investigated node.

Fig. 9: GraphLime results evaluated for 1866 nodes. Every row represents one node of the graph. The features with higher values are more important in the interpretation of the prediction of the given node.

D. Feature and Neighbor Impact Analysis on the Real Dataset

No ground truth data is available in the real dataset for validating the interpretation methods. However, the results are expected to meet some preliminary assumptions.

In an ideal situation, the network cells are entirely separated and do not interfere with each other. In practice, it is impossible to achieve; neighbor cells might impact one another in various ways. Some examples of the neighbor impact are listed in the following, noting that in future mobile network generations, even more complex scenarios might appear:

1) Neighbor cells (at different locations but next to each other) using the same or overlapping frequency bands: In this case, although the cells are separated in space, there might be radio disturbance (interference) typically at the cell

edge. We highlight two metrics as potential indicators of this impact, i) cell load: The higher traffic is generated in one cell (representing cell load), the higher the interference effect is. ii) number of users located near the edge of both cells: it also influences the significance of the neighbor impact. This number is cumbersome to measure in the network directly, though there are some measurable indicators that are in close relationship with it, e.g., the number of handovers between the two cells, indicating higher occurrence of the users near both cell edges.

2) Spectrum sharing between LTE and NR: When co-located cells of different technologies, such as LTE and NR, share the same radio resources, the high radio utilization (load) of one cell can negatively impact the performance of the other cell.

3) Multiple cells sharing transport links: In some rare cases, the transport link can be a bottleneck. High traffic generated in one cell (i.e., high load) might impact the performance of another cell sharing the same transport resources.

Based on these considerations, it is assumed that high network load is among the most probable reasons for neighbors' involvement in the target's KPI degradation. Another expectation is that the handover rate is higher when one node is affected by another.

An Ensemble GAT model was trained on the real dataset. For explainability validation purposes, the dataset was split into high and low KPI subsets during the test phase (no filtering was applied to the KPI in the training phase). For high KPI nodes, it is aimless to investigate the neighbor effect because none of the neighbors are expected to alter the KPI of the target node when the performance is at its peak. If GraphLime results were examined in a well-performing cell, we would find that some of the configuration related features would be highlighted. However, suppose feature impact analysis is conducted on poorly performing nodes. In that case, we find that in most of the cases, GraphLime does not give much weight to the configuration features but highlights the load features instead. Figure 10 depicts the GraphLime results of 282 nodes that were selected from the dataset based on two criteria: the KPI should be in the 3rd percentile or lower, and the aggregated neighbor impact should be higher than the 95th percentile. The aggregated neighbor impact was defined based on the Baseline model's output for the same nodes. For these nodes, it is assumed that the load of some neighboring cells have an impact on the KPI. Figure 10 shows that in most of these cases, GraphLime highlights some load features for explaining KPI degradation, as it is expected.

Neighbor Perturbation was also applied for the same 282 nodes with the same Ensemble GAT model. The nodes in this dataset have 49.4 neighbors on average. The average cardinality of the neighbor clusters selected by Neighbor Perturbation was 2.8, meaning that only a small subset of the neighbors were selected as important. It is expected that the neighbors that have an impact on the target's KPI have a higher load and a higher handover rate than the rest of the neighbors. Figure 11 shows the distribution of the handovers and three load features averaged node-by-node in the set of chosen neighbors and in the set of the rest of the nodes. As it can be observed, the chosen subset contains higher values on

Fig. 10: GraphLime results of low KPI cells, where the Baseline model indicates high neighbor load impact. Every row represents a low KPI node. In most of the cases GraphLime highlights some load features as explanations for the KPI degradation.

average in the case of all of these features. This result meets the preliminary expectations.

Fig. 11: Neighbor Perturbation results of low KPI cells with high neighbor load impact according to the Baseline model. The distribution of the handovers and three load feature values were compared for the neighbors chosen by Neighbor Perturbation and the rest of the neighbors. As it is expected, the chosen clusters have higher handover rates and higher load.

1) *Comparison with the Baseline:* In Table III it was already shown that the predictive power of the Baseline and the Ensemble GAT model are on the same magnitude. The real power of the Ensemble GAT model against the Baseline lies in the extension of prediction interpretations to the neighboring cells. Before diving into the comparison of the two explainers, we need to make some notes about their comparability:

- The complex causal relations of the features in the real dataset makes the interpretation of feature attributions difficult. The Baseline model is equipped to deal with causality by using the conditional asymmetric SHAP model, however, for the Ensemble GraphLime feature

attributions, following the causal relations more closely is still subject of future work.

- Another difference between them is that the feature importance values of the two models are on different scales. The GraphLime results are always positive and are normalized to sum up to one, whereas the SHAP values of the Baseline can take negative values as well and are not normalized.

In the real dataset the vast majority of the cells perform well and KPI degradation is considered to be a rare event. Before comparing the two model's ability to reveal the root-causes of KPI degradation, we needed to construct a test dataset from only those cells that present a decline in performance at some point of time. As a first step, we created a 23-element vector for each cell, which contained the KPI values of the given node in chronological order. After applying Principal Component Analysis [51] on these vectors, we were able to isolate 42 cases, in which a well performing cell's performance drops significantly during peak hours, when the network load is expected to be higher than usual.

Fig. 12: Comparison of Ensemble GraphLime and Baseline feature impact results of the same node for 23 consecutive snapshots. The x-axis indicates the hour of the day.

The feature attribution comparison of the Baseline model and Ensemble GraphLime is shown on Figure 12 for one of these cells. For easier interpretation, the features have been categorized into 11 categories. Note that the baseline model has an extra category for the features that involve aggregated neighbor information (neighbor_load). Since the Ensemble GAT model have access to neighbor information by design, the features corresponding to this category were left out from its training. It can be observed that both models shift the importance of the categories as the KPI (average

downlink throughput) decreases around peak time (starting at around 10 o'clock). The neighbor load feature category of the Baseline model strengthens with negative importance, indicating that there are some neighbors that negatively affect the local cell's performance. However, a detailed explanation of this neighbor effect is missing. By comparing this outcome with the Ensemble GraphLime results on the lower figure, a more detailed assessment of the neighbor effect can be seen: the load, interference and channel quality features become more prominent. At the same time the importance of the CM dimensioning features drops dramatically.

Fig. 13: Ensemble GraphLime (Ens.GL) and Baseline feature impact values averaged in the lowest five (\mathcal{L}) and in the highest five (\mathcal{H}) KPI points for 42 cells with KPI degradation.

The output of the two methods were analysed for all the 42 cells with KPI degradation. To be able to differentiate between the high and low KPI results, the dataset of the 42 cells was sampled to form datasets \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{H} , the sets of the five lowest and five highest KPI points of each cell respectively. Since 5 snapshots were chosen for each of the 42 cells, the cardinality of the sets is $|\mathcal{L}| = |\mathcal{H}| = 210$.

On Figure 13 the results of the different nodes were averaged and compared in \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{H} . The Baseline model signals KPI degradation by showing load and neighbor load attributes in the negative range. Both models have a strong emphasis on the configuration related CM dimensioning category. In case of the Baseline model the impact of this category is the same for high and low KPI points. Whereas for the Ensembled GraphLime model the effect of this category is reduced when the KPI is degraded and a significant part of it is replaced by load, interference and channel quality related feature attributions.

2) *Local and External Effect Separation*: The attention coefficients of the Ensembled GAT model (see equation (3) in Section III-C1.) allow for a deeper insight into the calculation of the predictions and make the model itself partly interpretable. Since during the GAT training self-loops were added to every node, these coefficients are also present locally and can be used to isolate the effect of the neighbors from the local effects.

The behavior of the self-loop attention scores was analysed

in dataset \mathcal{L} . Let n^t be the representation of cell n in snapshot t , aw_{n^t} the attention coefficient corresponding to node n in snapshot t and let n_i^t ($i \in \{0, \dots, k\}$) be the representation of $k+1$ neighbors of node n in snapshot t . For every $n^t \in \mathcal{L}$,

$$\delta = aw_{n^t} - \frac{\sum_{i=0}^k aw_{n_i^t}}{k+1}$$

was computed to investigate the difference between the local attention coefficient and the mean of the neighbors' attention values. The bigger δ is, the stronger the local effect is according to the model. Since \mathcal{L} is the collection of the data points where high load is the most probable cause of the KPI degradation, we anticipate that the load of the nodes with higher δ values should be also high.

Fig. 14: Comparison of local and neighbor load averages in different percentile intervals of δ in set \mathcal{L} .

Figure 14 shows the comparison of local and neighbor load feature averages in the different percentile intervals of δ . As δ , the difference between the local and neighbor average attention coefficient is getting bigger, higher local load can be observed, meaning that the attention coefficient on the self-loop is a valuable measure for estimating the impact of the local features compared to the external effects.

The attention coefficients corresponding to the neighbors were also investigated on dataset \mathcal{L} , and the results were compared to the output of Neighbor Perturbation. After selecting the most impacting neighbors in dataset \mathcal{L} with Neighbor Perturbation, we repeated the selection with another method that was based on the attention coefficients. Several experiments have been conducted with different versions for this neighbor selection process, including threshold settings on the attention score and choosing the neighbors with the n highest values. Since there was no significant difference in the outputs, we present only one version with the most reliable results: for every node, only one neighbor is selected, the one that belongs to the maximum attention coefficient. In Figure 15, the distribution of two load features is compared in the chosen/not chosen sets of the two methods. The nodes chosen by Neighbor Perturbation exhibit a higher load relative to the load of the unchosen set, whereas in the case of the attention score-based method, a much smaller difference can be observed.

These results show that in the case of KPI degradation, a high attention coefficient on the self-loop is a good measure of

Fig. 15: The comparison of the empirical cumulative distribution functions of the two most impacting features (according to the Ensembled GraphLime method) in the sets of chosen/not chosen neighbors selected by Neighbor Perturbation and by the highest attention coefficients.

the local impact. However, when self-attention is low relative to the attention corresponding to the neighbors, Neighbor Perturbation is a more reliable method for choosing the most impacting neighbors.

VI. APPLICATION

Service assurance and network optimization are important tasks to provide high-quality networking services. With the increasing complexity of the evolving networks, automation solutions are required to reduce the expensive human effort and decrease the time to reach the optimal settings. There are many factors in the network optimization problem, e.g., the traffic demand of the users is dynamically changing in time and space; new service types are emerging from time to time; many tradeoffs appear in network operations involving cost, performance, and energy consumption; handling errors, faults, malfunctioning devices is unavoidable; to mention a few. Performance degradation in the network is considered a high priority. In an optimization loop, finding the root cause of the problem is the first step, and then actuation steps can be determined to cease or alleviate the problem.

The Ensemble GAT method described in this paper can be applied to find the root cause of the performance degradation automatically, especially focusing on neighbor cell impact. Separating the local and neighbor effects and highlighting the most impacting neighbor cells is highly important to find the best action to resolve the problem.

A. Use case example

Explainable GNN-based methods are applicable in any RAN use cases where the impact of the neighbor cells is important. We show an example where the dynamics and tradeoffs are significant: Cell shaping is the automated process

of setting and fine-tuning the cell coverage area by adjusting certain parameters such as antenna tilt and power. In this mechanism, both the current cell and the neighboring cells are affected, so coordination between the cells is essential.

In the cell shaping mechanism, the users located at the border of the neighboring cells are affected to the largest extent, active UEs near the cell edge might be handed over to the neighboring cell. This way, some important metrics such as the number of users, the load, the signal strength, and the interference are subject to change, resulting in changes in the main performance metrics such as throughput, session drop ratio, and handover success ratio.

The problem of antenna tilt optimization is widely studied with various methods; we refer to [52] and [53] and the references therein for further information. In all cases, automated cell shaping is an iterative process, where the main metrics and the performance are evaluated after each new setting is applied. This evaluation is complex since the performance is impacted by many factors. The potential of using the Ensemble GAT is twofold here. One potential application is to set the right direction and right amount in a given cell to change based on the prediction of the performance. For example, the antenna tilt for cell A is recommended to increase by 1 degree to potentially get better performance. Another application is to evaluate the main impacting features and the main impacting neighbors after the new settings to determine whether the change in performance was due to new parameter settings or other external factors. This way, an algorithm can decide more quickly and reliably when to keep the new settings and when to revert to the old one.

B. Practical considerations

Finally, some thoughts on the practical usage of the Ensemble GAT method are shared.

1) Since the method is utilizing the whole network graph, it should be deployed as a central network management function. Other methods such as local models or distributed learning methods are more suitable for optimization functions running locally in the base station.

2) High-quality network observability is key to applying machine learning in root cause analysis and network optimization. The right parameters should be reported in the right granularity, otherwise, basic relations are not captured well.

3) In a multi-vendor environment, i.e., where neighboring base stations are from different vendors, the measured parameters might not be the same, or if they measure the same metric, they might be represented in a different way. In this case, adaptation is needed between the sets of parameters of the different vendors in order to be able to use them in the same GAT model.

4) Though the explainability method proposed in this paper identifies the neighboring cell and the features that affect the decision most significantly, its outcome is still too low level for human network operators and may require the application of other methods like generative AI, symbolic representation or advanced feature visualization techniques to improve the interpretability of results. As described in [54], the development

of tools that can communicate the results of explainability methods to users and engineers better is still an open issue of XAI research.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we proposed the Ensemble GAT model for network KPI prediction. The model can handle the time evolution of the parameters in the graph nodes (i.e., multiple snapshots) and provides as good results as state-of-the-art on both synthetic and real datasets. We also presented the method of Neighbor Perturbation and showed that it can identify the impacting neighbors of a cell. To find the impacting features, we demonstrated that GraphLime is a reliable choice and can highlight the important local and neighbor features that are not possible with conventional methods using tabular datasets. We showed that these two explanation methods are consistent (Neighbor Perturbation selects the neighbor with the highest GraphLime features), and by using them together with the Ensemble GAT model, we can gain valuable insights into the root causes of network KPI degradations. However, resolving the causal relations of the feature attributions is still a task of future work.

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